

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSING CROSS-SENSITIZATION IN CHILDREN WITH ATOPIC DERMATITIS

O.A. Nazarov¹, M.N. Abdullayeva²

TashPMI, Tashkent, Uzbekistan^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14978061>

Abstract. Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disease often accompanied by polysensitization to various allergens. Cross-sensitization is an immunological phenomenon in which patients develop allergic reactions to multiple unrelated allergens due to similarities in their molecular structures. In children with AD, this process complicates diagnosis and requires a comprehensive approach.

Diagnosing cross-sensitization in children with AD includes skin allergy tests, detection of specific IgE antibodies, molecular allergy diagnostics, and provocation tests. Anamnesis and consideration of potential food, pollen, and household allergens play a crucial role. Modern methods, such as component-resolved diagnostics, help clarify the spectrum of sensitization and minimize unnecessary dietary and treatment restrictions. Early and accurate diagnosis of cross-sensitization in children with AD contributes to personalized therapy and improves patients' quality of life.

Keywords: atopic dermatitis, cross-sensitization, specific IgE, exoallergens.

Relevance: Over the past decades, allergic diseases (Ads) have become widespread not only in developing countries but also in developed European nations. With increasing urbanization, there is a rising trend in allergic diseases among children and adults. Clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis are observed in 70–90% of infants during their first year of life. The increasing incidence of this pathology is associated with several objective factors: rising emissions from vehicle exhaust, environmental pollution from industrial and household waste, expanded use of pharmaceuticals, and the widespread use of chemical substances in everyday life. Some researchers also note that the increased frequency of allergic disease diagnoses is linked to improved medical diagnostic capabilities and enhanced epidemiological research (Diaz-Sanchez, 2000). In most cases, allergic reactions in children are of an atopic nature. The first researcher to describe the phenomenon of atopy was J. B. Helmont in 1607, noting the link between asthma and skin itching. In 1923, A. F. Coca and R. A. Cooke introduced the term “atopy” (from the Greek Atopia—“strange” or “unusual”), describing genetically determined forms of hypersensitivity (asthma, hay fever). Later, in 1931, A. F. Coca classified food and drug intolerance as atopic diseases, and in 1933, F. Wise and V. D. Sulzberger expanded the definition by introducing the term “atopic dermatitis.” Atopic dermatitis (AD) is more common in girls than in boys. The disease is diagnosed in 50% of children with allergic conditions before the age of two, and in 60% of cases in children over two years old. In the same age group, asthma symptoms are observed in 40% of children, and signs of allergic rhinitis in 25%. According to the scientific and practical program “Atopic Dermatitis in Children”, developed by the Russian Association, AD is defined as “a chronic allergic skin disease accompanied by an increased level of serological IgE and hypersensitivity to specific allergens.”

Cross-sensitization to heterologous allergens significantly complicates the clinical course of AD and makes its treatment more challenging. According to international ISSAC studies conducted in 56 countries, the prevalence of atopic dermatitis among preschool children ranges from 1.1% in Iran to over 16% in Japan and Sweden. In the 13–14-year-old age group, the data variation is even greater, from 1% in Albania to 17% in Nigeria.

In Russia, the prevalence of AD among children ranges from 5.2% to 17.4%. In the Moscow region, symptoms of atopic dermatitis are detected in 6.17% of children, whereas in European countries, the incidence is 2–3 times higher (according to various sources, up to 20% of schoolchildren exhibit AD symptoms).

AD is more common in children under five years of age, with symptoms appearing in 48–75% of cases before six months of age. If both parents have atopic dermatitis, the likelihood of its development in a child is 81%; if one parent has AD and the other has respiratory allergies, the probability is 59%; if only one parent has AD, the risk is 56%.

Although genetic predisposition plays a significant role in AD development, it does not fully explain the sharp rise in incidence. Various hypotheses have been proposed, including the “hygiene hypothesis,” which suggests that reduced microbial exposure in early childhood due to high hygiene standards leads to a predominance of the Th2 immune response in genetically predisposed children. This hypothesis explains the higher prevalence of AD in developed countries compared to developing ones, where there is an increase in diseases associated with Th1 response activation. However, studies by Nisheva E. S., Peshekhonova Yu. V., and colleagues (2004) questioned the Th1/Th2 imbalance hypothesis as the primary mechanism for allergic diseases. They proposed an alternative theory suggesting that macrophage dysfunction plays a key role, leading to discoordination of humoral and cellular immune responses. In recent years, the clinical course of AD has changed. More complicated forms of the disease are increasingly observed, often associated with secondary bacterial or fungal infections. It has been established that yeast fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Pityrosporum*, etc.) have high sensitizing activity in AD, mediated by elevated IgE levels. Additionally, atopic dermatitis often precedes the development of respiratory allergies caused by inhalant allergens, confirming the concept of the “atopic march”—the sequential development of allergic diseases in predisposed children.

Objective of the Study

To examine the clinical features of atopic dermatitis in children with combined sensitization to various allergens using modern *in vitro* allergy diagnostic methods.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in two stages.

- **Stage 1:** A survey was conducted, during which data were collected through interviews with the child and family members.
- **Stage 2:** Clinical and laboratory examinations were performed in an outpatient setting.

A total of 42 children aged 5 to 11 years were surveyed and examined. Standardized allergens were used for allergy testing. The concentrations of total and specific IgE in serum were determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) in a "sandwich" format with ELISA kits—total IgE produced by Alcor Bio (Russia).

The study group included 42 children with IgE-mediated atopic dermatitis, with an average age of 7.98 ± 0.18 years. Of these, 77% were girls, and 23% were boys.

Results and Discussion

The survey revealed that a family history of allergic diseases in one or more immediate relatives (siblings, mother, or father) was present in 88.2% of children. Atopic diseases were found in one immediate relative in 36 children (85.2%), while in 6 children (14.8%), two immediate relatives had atopic diseases.

Complicated pregnancies were reported in 59% of cases. Antibiotics were administered during the neonatal period to 47% of children. Clinically significant gastrointestinal disorders (unstable stools, presence of leukocytes and mucus in stool analysis) were observed in 32% of patients.

An analysis of the medical history showed that 45% of women during pregnancy and 47% of mothers during breastfeeding consumed dairy products in amounts ranging from 1 to 1.5 liters per day, which is twice the recommended intake for healthy pregnant women in the second half of pregnancy.

Clinical symptoms manifested in:

- 44.6% of cases as oral allergic syndrome,
- 51% as gastrointestinal symptoms,
- 36% as respiratory symptoms,
- 29% as skin manifestations.

The time for the first symptoms to appear after consuming the "culprit" food allergen was **21.2 ± 13.9 minutes**.

According to the clinical questionnaire, **25%** of patients showed sensitivity to only one food allergen, while **75%** identified more than one food trigger for allergic reactions. In children with polyvalent sensitization, atopic dermatitis developed significantly earlier than in those sensitized to a single food allergen.

Spectrum of Allergens Identified by Specific IgE in Serum:

Gastrointestinal disturbances were noted in:

- **60%** of patients after consuming milk,
- **35%** after consuming eggs and apples,
- **15%** after consuming tomatoes,
- **12%** after consuming peaches,
- **8%** after consuming peanuts,
- **7%** after consuming carrots.

Respiratory symptoms were associated with:

- **25%** of cases for milk and eggs,
- **5%** for apples,
- **15%** for tomatoes,
- **8%** for peaches and peanuts,
- **15%** for carrots.

Skin reactions occurred after consuming:

- **42%** of cases for milk,
- **35%** for eggs,
- **5%** for apples,
- **18%** for tomatoes,
- **8%** for peaches,

- **15%** for peanuts,
- **8%** for carrots.

In all the groups mentioned, serum IgE levels were elevated above **250.5 IU/mL**.

Conclusion

Several sets of criteria have been proposed for diagnosing atopic dermatitis (AD). While they are primarily used in epidemiological studies, they also serve as guidelines for clinical diagnosis.

Diagnostic Criteria for Atopic Dermatitis

UK Working Group Criteria

The UK Working Group includes one mandatory and five main criteria but does not incorporate the allergy criteria initially proposed by Hanifin and Rajka.

Mandatory Criterion:

- Skin itching, including reports from parents or guardians that the child rubs or scratches.

Additional Criteria (three or more required for diagnosis):

- History of involvement of skin folds (elbow and popliteal creases, neck, areas around the eyes, and the front of the ankles).
- A history of asthma or hay fever (or the presence of atopic disease in close relatives of children under 4 years old).
- General skin dryness within the past year.
- Symptom onset before the age of two (not used for diagnosing children under four years old).
- Visible dermatitis affecting flexural surfaces (for children under four, this includes dermatitis on the cheeks, forehead, and outer surfaces of the limbs).

American Academy of Dermatology Criteria

These criteria include three groups of features: major, important, and associated.

Major Features (three or more required):

- Mild to severe itching.
- Eczematous dermatitis (acute, subacute, or chronic) with typical morphology and age-related characteristics:
 - Involvement of the face, neck, and extensor surfaces in infants and children under four years old.
 - Current or past involvement of flexural surfaces at any age.
- Chronic or recurrent disease course.

Important Features (two or more required):

- Disease onset before the age of two.
- Personal and/or family history of allergic rhinitis, asthma, food allergy, or atopic dermatitis.
- Skin dryness within the past year.
- History of involvement of skin folds (elbow and popliteal creases, neck, areas around the eyes, and the front of the ankles).
- A history of asthma or hay fever (or the presence of atopic disease in close relatives of children under four years old).

- Symptoms beginning before the age of two (not used for diagnosing children under four years old).

Associated Features (at least one required):

- Atypical vascular reactions (e.g., facial pallor, white dermographism, delayed blanching response).
- Follicular keratosis, pityriasis alba, hyperlinear palms, ichthyosis.
- Periocular changes (periorbital darkening or lichenification, bilateral periorbital eczema, Dennie-Morgan lines under the lower eyelids).
- Perioral eczema, bilateral periauricular eczematous lesions, prurigo nodules or papules.
- Perifollicular accentuation or lichenification.
- Sparring of the groin and axillary areas.

Skin Biopsy and Laboratory Tests

Skin biopsy and laboratory tests, including IgE level determination, are not routinely used for AD diagnosis and are not recommended. However, in certain cases, histological examination of skin biopsies or other laboratory tests (e.g., serum IgE determination, potassium hydroxide preparation, patch testing, genetic testing) may help rule out other skin diseases.

Clinical Features of Atopic Dermatitis with Concurrent Allergies

The development of hypersensitivity in AD patients occurs due to sequential sensitization to various allergens, including household, pollen, food, and other antigens, which can be significantly different from one another.

Atopic dermatitis with concurrent allergies presents with a more severe clinical course and may be associated with the following conditions:

- **Oral allergy syndrome.**
- **Allergic rhinitis.**
- **Atopic bronchial asthma.**

Determining the type of sensitization in AD allows for timely prognosis of disease progression and helps in developing targeted etiopathogenetic treatment strategies.

REFERENCES

1. Baranov A.A., Balabolkin I.I. *Pediatric Allergology. A Guide for Physicians*. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media, 2006. 668 p.
2. Luss I.V., Repina T.Y. *Allergens and Hidden Allergens. What's the Difference?* Russian Allergology Journal, No. 6, 2009, pp. 46–47.
3. Kolkhir P.V. *Evidence-Based Allergology and Immunology*. Moscow, 2010, pp. 38–39.
4. *Allergology: Federal Clinical Guidelines*. R.M. Khaitov, N.I. Ilyina. Moscow, 2014, pp. 25–26.
5. Nazarov A.A., Tukhtaeva O.T. *Clinical Allergology*. Tashkent, 2022, pp. 254–255.
6. Frank M.M. *Complement Deficiencies*. Pediatric Clinics of North America, 2000, Vol. 47, pp. 1337–1354.
7. Johansson S.G., Bousquet J., et al. *A Revised Nomenclature for Allergy*, 2001, Vol. 56, pp. 813–824.